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ADAPT

NORTHERN HERITAGE

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05 & 06 MAY 2020

Adapting historic places to climate change

*Proceedings of the international virtual conference
of the project Adapt Northern Heritage*

Northern Periphery and
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2014–2020

EUROPEAN UNION

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Acknowledgements

The conference was run by the Project Partners of the project [Adapt Northern Heritage \(2017-2020\)](#), namely [Historic Environment Scotland](#), [Minjastofnun Islands](#), [Norsk institutt for kulturminneforskning](#) and [Riksantikvaren](#), for which they received funding from the European Union, Iceland and Norway through the [Interreg Programme for the Northern Periphery and Arctic](#).

The Project Partners wish to extend their sincere thanks to the individuals and organisations that contributed their time and expertise in reviewing submissions. Further, a special thanks to all speakers, chairs and facilitators involved.

Editors

Gemma Houston, Vanessa Glindmeier, Carsten Hermann (Historic Environment Scotland)

Version V1.0 published May 2020

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Cover image

The monastery of the Solovetsky Islands in Russia’s White Sea is a northern UNESCO World Heritage site and a case study in the project Adapt Northern Heritage. The archipelago features in three of the papers / presentations of the conference.

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Hygrothermal performance of an old building with log walls from the region of Vestfold in Norway

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Abstract

Emphasis is currently given to the impact of climate change on cultural heritage sites and buildings. In this study the climate change impact on the hygrothermal performance and the biodeterioration risk of an historic timber building is examined. The investigated construction is a two-storey building located in southern Norway and dates back to 1407. In-situ inspection revealed that the building elements are significantly damaged by fungi. Sensors have been installed inside the building in order to monitor air temperatures and relative humidity responsible for the observed damages. Moreover, climate data for the past and potential future scenarios have been acquired and used as an input in hygrothermal simulations of typical cross sections of the log walls. The calculated transient hygrothermal conditions serve as input parameters to the biohygrothermal model that is used for the assessment of the biodeterioration risk. The findings reveal insignificant mold risk. However, mold indices predicted for the future years have far higher values than the ones predicted under current conditions, which indicates the need for further and more detailed investigation.

Keywords – Historic building; biodeterioration; climate change; hygrothermal modelling

1. Introduction

Several studies underline the dramatic changes that are expected to take place in nature and environment due to the climate change [1]. In Norway, long-term climate projections up to the year 2100 have demonstrated that the country will face an increase of annual temperature up to 6.4°C and precipitation up to 18% [2]. Higher temperature and humidity levels will intensify the decay of the building materials in historic structures resulting to irreversible damages [3]. Timber historic buildings are mostly at risk because of their vulnerability to biodeterioration, such as fungi that germinate favourably under the predicted future climate conditions [3,4].

The purpose of this work is to assess the climate change impact on the biodegradation of the log walls of an historic timber construction in southern Norway. In the framework of this study both measurements and simulations are employed. The measurements concern the monitoring of the indoor environment of the building. The set of the numerical simulations is consisted of i) a hygrothermal model employed for the estimation of the temperature and moisture content in the building components and ii) a biohygrothermal model used to assess

the mould risk on various cross sections of the logs on the basis of the temperature and moisture content results.

2. Methodology

2.1 Experimental site

The building under investigation is located in southern Norway, in the county of Vestfold (Fig. 1). It was built in 1407 in the region of Heierstad and thus it got the name 'Heirastad loft'. In 1957, it was moved approximately 50km south to the Slottsfjellet hill (Fig. 1), in Tønsberg, where it still stands as a property of the Slottsfjell museum. Its current location is 250m far from the coast and on 50m above the sea level.

Figure 7. On the left, a map of Norway with the county of Vestfold highlighted with red and on the right a closer view of the Slottsfjellet hill where the historic building is located

The two-storey building is founded on rocks (Fig. 2). It has a rectangular plan with its entrance in the north-west façade (Fig. 2). It is constructed of large softwood logs, most likely Scots Pine, i.e. *pinus sylvestris*, or Norway Spruce, i.e. *picea abies*, treated with tar on their outer surface. In the upper floor there are openings in the south-west, north-west and north-east facade allowing significant natural ventilation, while in the lower floor there are no wide openings. The building has a simple gable roof made of coarse wooden boards, a layer of birch bark and turf.

Figure 2. The Heierstad loft as observed (a) from a satellite view and (b) on site picture from south-west

The building is generally in good condition but requires continuous maintenance. The log walls of the ground floor are preserved unaltered since 1407. The upper floor was reconstructed in 1957 when the Heierstad loft was moved to the Slottsfjellet hill. Furthermore, the latest reconstruction of the roof took place in 2019. The in-situ inspection revealed that the exterior side of the log walls have cracks in several positions with the bigger examples having an average width of 0.03m and depth of 0.05m. Inside the cracks the nutritious wood that is unveiled in combination with the prevailing ambient conditions, mainly water from rising damp, condensation or rain that penetrates the cracks, form the appropriate environment for mold growth (Fig. 3(a)). Fungal growth has also been detected in the ground floor of the building in positions close to leakages (Fig. 3(b)) and joints (Fig. 3(c) and (d)). Biodeterioration damage of the log walls of the upper level is less severe.

Figure 3. Fungal decay in the building's (a) exterior and (b), (c), (d) interior

2.2 Experimental set-up

Three sensors having the characteristics described in Table 1 have been installed in the building in order to monitor the climatic conditions responsible for the observed damage (Fig. 4). The first sensor is in the upper floor close to the north-west oriented opening (Fig.4(b)). The second sensor is in the middle of the largest room of the upper level of the building (Fig.4(b)) and the

third sensor is in the ground floor (Fig.4(a)). For the purpose of this study a five-week period of measurements has been processed, starting from the 14th of October 2019.

Table 5. Characteristics of the sensors installed in the Heierstad loft

Parameter	Units	Range	Accuracy	Interval
Air temperature	°C	-40°C to +70°C	±1°C	30 min
Relative humidity	-	0 to 100%	±5%	30 min
Dew point	°C	-40°C to +70°C	±2°C	30 min

Figure 4. Sensors position in (a) the ground floor and (b) the upper floor

2.3 Assessment of the current and future climate conditions

Climate data of temperature (ϑ), precipitation (RR), relative humidity (φ), wind speed (FF) and direction (DD), shortwave global (H_{Gh}) and diffuse (H_{Dh}) radiation, longwave radiation (G_{Lin}) and cloud cover (N) were generated for the project's site (latitude: 59.2744° N, longitude: 10.4036° E, and altitude: 50m) for both past and potential future years [5]. The past climate conditions are represented by a typical year consisted of data from the period 1991-2010 for radiation and 2000-2009 for the rest of the climate parameters. The analysed future conditions correspond to the years 2050 and 2100, under the Standardized Reference Emission Scenarios (SRES) B1 and A2 of the fourth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) [6].

From the climate data referring to the past years [5], it is observed that the prevailing temperatures are low with an annual average of 7.8°C (Fig. 5(a)). Precipitation is moderate and well distributed throughout the year, with a mean annual value of 685mm (Fig 6). Relative

humidity remains in high levels during the whole year having a mean annual value of 76%. Relative humidity fluctuates around 70% during spring and summer and around 80% during autumn and winter. In addition, the mean monthly wind speed fluctuates between 3.5m/s and 5m/s (gentle breeze, according to the Beaufort scale), while the predominant wind direction is from South. The solar radiation related parameters vary extremely over the course of the year. The energy absorbed by a horizontal surface due to short-wave radiation reaches a maximum during June with a mean monthly value of 238W/m². Almost half of this energy corresponds to the contribution of diffuse radiation. On the other hand, during December the mean monthly global radiation is only 6W/m². The cloud cover fraction fluctuates between 4 and 7 octas, with the lower values occurring during summer. Finally, the average hourly long-wave radiation from the sky fluctuates between 260W/m² and 35W/m², with the lowest values occurring during winter and the highest ones during summer.

Figure 5. Mean monthly (a) air temperature and (b) precipitation for past and potential future (under SRES B1 and A2) years for the project's site

According to the data referring to the future conditions, most of the climate parameters change slightly or do not change at all. The most significant changes are predicted for temperature and precipitation (Fig. 5 (a) and (b)), the mean annual values of which are predicted to increase by 1.2°C and 36% in 2100 under the SRES A2. Temperature predictions for the other three examined scenarios (SRES B1 and A2 for 2050 and SRES B1 for 2100) indicate a decrease in air temperature during the coldest months of the year. The temperature decrease contradicts to other studies [5] and, thus, these three scenarios are not considered as potential future climate profiles.

2.4 Bio- and hygrothermal simulations

Within this study a one-dimensional hygrothermal simulation tool [7] has been used to calculate the temperature and water content of the building elements. The transient hygrothermal boundary conditions serve as the input parameters to the biohygrothermal model [8] used to predict the risk of mould growth on the building components. Within the biohygrothermal simulations a biodegradable substrate material is considered. The biohygrothermal model incorporates a transformation function allowing the expression of mould risk in terms of mould index [9].

2.4.1 Geometry, Material Properties and Boundary Conditions

Four different geometries are modelled in the one-dimensional hygrothermal simulator. The first one represents the exterior log walls that typically have a thickness of $d_{log}= 0.20\text{m}$ and are treated with tar in their outer surface ($S_d= 10\text{m}$) (Fig. 7(a)). The second one corresponds to the exterior walls in positions that have cracks. In that case the thickness of the wall is $d_{log,crack}= 0.15\text{m}$ and the tar treatment is considered to be removed ($S_d=0$) (Fig. 7(a)). The third represents the interior log walls (Fig. 7(b)) and the fourth one the timber floors (Fig. 7(c) and (d)). All analysed building components are made of softwood with the physical, thermal and hygric properties presented in Table 2 [7].

Table 2. Physical, thermal and hygric properties of softwood walls

Bulk density	Porosity	Specific heat capacity	Thermal conductivity	Water vapor diffusion resistance factor
ρ [kg/m ³]	ε [m ³ /m ³]	c_p [J/(kg K)]	λ [W/m K]	μ [-]
450	0.73	1500	0.09	200

In the framework of the simulations it is assumed that the exterior walls are exposed to rain, wind, short and long-wave radiation, ambient air temperature and relative humidity on their outer side, while on their inner side they are exposed to the indoor temperature and relative humidity (Fig. 6(a)). The interior walls are exposed in both their sides to the ambient temperature and relative humidity (Fig 6(b)) and the same applies to the floor configurations. It is also assumed that the indoor air temperature and relative humidity are equal to the

outdoor ones. This hypothesis is reasonable, since the building has neither transparent elements nor Heating Ventilation and Air Conditioning (HVAC) system. The hygrothermal performance of the building components is assessed for the 10th year of the computational simulation, so that the results are not affected by initial conditions.

Figure 6. Boundary conditions and dimensions of the simulated assemblies

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Measurements

In Fig. 7(a) and (b) air temperature and relative humidity measurements from the sensors and Melsom weather station (5km far from the pilot area) can be seen. Air temperature measurements (Fig. 7(a)) from the sensors are consistent with the ones from the nearby weather station, while the differences appearing in the relative humidity measurements (Fig. 7(b)) are due to the fact that the pilot area is closer to the sea compared to the weather station. Among the sensors higher range and lower mean value of air temperature is monitored first by sensor 1, then sensor 2 and last sensor 3 (Fig. 7(a)). Thus, it is revealed that the ground level is less exposed to the outdoors conditions. Furthermore, the relative humidity measurements from sensor 3 have an average value of 88% and in all cases are higher than 72%. This reveals that that the ground floor cannot be easily discharged from high moisture levels. These observations are of course linked to the poor ventilation of the ground floor and can interpret the more severe damage by fungi.

Figure 7. Measurements of (a) temperature and (b) relative humidity

3.2 Mould Risk

In Table 3 the resulted mould indices for all modelled assemblies under past and potential future conditions are presented. In all cases the mould index is calculated for a one-year period. Results reveal that there isn't significant mould risk. However, comparing the mould indices of the past years to the future ones, an increasing trend can be observed. The highest mould indices are calculated for the interior walls, while the maximum increase of the mould index is projected for the positions with cracks in the exterior walls.

It is worth mentioning that the values of the mould index are highly dependent on the climate conditions and the material properties that are considered within the hygrothermal simulations. In order to simulate more accurately the physical problem, it is important to use non-destructive methods in order to define the exact material properties. It is, also, important to take into account more scenarios about the future climate.

Table 3. Mould indices for the log walls estimated for a one-year period under past and potential future climate

Assembly	Orientation	Mould index			
		Past		Future	
		Outer surface	Inner surface	Outer surface	Inner surface
Exterior wall treated with tar	North-West	0.000	0.086	0.000	0.118
	North-East	0.000	0.092	0.000	0.120
	South-East	0.000	0.072	0.000	0.097
	South-West	0.000	0.066	0.000	0.092
Exterior wall in position with crack	North-West	0.067	0.082	0.112	0.115
	North-East	0.063	0.089	0.117	0.118
	South-East	0.049	0.073	0.074	0.097
	South-West	0.048	0.065	0.071	0.090
Interior wall	All	0.188		0.205	
Floor	All	0.179	0.187	0.194	0.203

4. Conclusions

In this study the degradation of a timber historic building in southern Norway is examined. In-situ inspection revealed that the most critical damage on the building elements is fungal attack. More severe damage has been observed in the ground level which is poorly ventilated. Moreover, measurements from sensors confirmed that higher mean air temperature occurs in the ground level. It was also observed that the ground level cannot be easily discharged from high moisture levels. One-dimensional models of the building elements were investigated for their hygrothermal performance under past and potential future climate conditions. The calculated hygrothermal conditions were then used as an input in biohygrothermal simulations to assess the risk of mould growth on the building material surfaces. Results have shown insignificant mould risk. However, higher mould indices have been projected for the future years, with the maximum increase projected for the exterior surfaces in positions with cracks. It is worth mentioning that in a future study more climate change scenarios should be taken into account and also the actual material properties of the analysed building elements should be defined by non-destructive methods.

This work is a part of the HYPERION project. HYPERION has received funding from the European Union's Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (Horizon 2020) under the No 821054 grant agreement. The contents of this publication are the sole responsibility of Oslo Metropolitan University and do not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union.

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